
The Role of Public Diplomacy in Promoting Nigeria's National Interest In the 21st Century

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the Role of Public Diplomacy in Promoting Nigeria's National Interest in The 21st Century. The paper employed the theory of soft power as its theoretical framework. The theory was first proposed by Joseph Nye in 1990. The theory helps understand how nations achieve their objectives by attracting others rather than forcing them. This paper adopted a qualitative research methodology and relies on secondary sources of data collection to examine the role of public diplomacy in promoting Nigeria's national interest in the 21st century. Data were sourced from academic journals, textbooks, etc. Content analysis was used as the method of data analysis. The paper found that public diplomacy has emerged as an important instrument in Nigeria's foreign policy, which is used to achieve the country's political, economic, security, socio-cultural, regional, and global interests. The paper also reveals the history of public diplomacy in Nigeria, which has evolved from liberation and peacekeeping activities in the 1960s and 1970s, to economic diplomacy in the 1980s, citizen diplomacy in the 2000s, and finally to diaspora and digital diplomacy in the 21st century. Finally some of the instruments used by Nigeria in its public diplomacy, such as peacekeeping, the Technical Aid Corps, Nollywood, remittance, cultural exchange, regional mediation, and digital communication. It recommends that Nigeria needs to develop an overall national public diplomacy strategy that articulates national interests, national public diplomacy goals, target audiences, as well as methods of communication, online presence of Nigerian embassies needs to be enhanced. Additionally, there is a need to utilize strategic communication to project Nigeria's image abroad.

KEYWORDS: Public Diplomacy, Soft Power, Digital Diplomacy, Cultural Diplomacy, National Security, Foreign Policy Etc.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
17 June 2026

Available on:
<https://ijiissh.com/>

INTRODUCTION

In the modern international system, public diplomacy has emerged as one of the significant means of advancing national interests. In the past, diplomacy was restricted to government relations; however, the impact of globalisation and the emergence of new technologies have broadened its scope to incorporate publics abroad and international organisations. Public diplomacy can be defined as the means by which a state uses communication, cultural exchange programmes, international broadcasting, educational exchange programmes, and diaspora engagement to shape publics abroad and to advance its national interest. In the modern international system of the 21st century, public diplomacy has emerged as one of the significant aspects of foreign policy because a state's image and reputation play a vital role in attracting foreign investment and support in the international system (Gurgu, & Cociuban, 2016).

Nigeria's public diplomacy history began in the year 1960 when Nigeria attained independence and began pursuing an African-centred foreign policy with the primary objective of advancing African unity, decolonisation, and peace in the region (Williams, 2025). During this period, Nigeria employed peacekeeping operations, technical assistance, and cultural engagement as tools of public diplomacy in advancing Nigeria's role in Africa. For example, Nigeria has participated in several United Nations peacekeeping operations in Congo in 1960, Lebanon in 1978, Liberia in 1990, Sierra Leone in 1999, and Sudan in 2005, which boosted Nigeria's international reputation as a peacekeeping nation and enhanced Nigeria's foreign policy influence in Africa (Bukar, & Ngada, 2019). Nigeria further enhanced its public diplomacy by providing technical and development assistance to developing countries through the Nigerian Technical Aid Corps (NTAC), established in 1987. The Technical Aid Corps sent

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Nigerian professionals such as doctors, teachers, engineers, and agricultural experts to developing countries in Africa, the Caribbean, and the Pacific as part of Nigeria's foreign policy and public diplomacy strategy (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). Between 1987 and 2020, the Technical Aid Corps sent over 10,000 Nigerian professionals to over 40 countries, thereby enhancing Nigeria's bilateral relations and cultural diplomacy/soft power capabilities in these countries (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018).

In the 21st century, diaspora diplomacy has emerged as one of the most important tools of Nigeria's public diplomacy. The Nigerian diaspora plays a crucial role in the Nigerian economy. Remittances, investments, and knowledge transfer are some of the ways the diaspora contributes to the economy. In the year 2018, Nigeria received diaspora remittances amounting to around \$21 billion. This figure makes Nigeria the largest diaspora remittance receiver in Africa and one of the top receivers globally (Mbaye, Tani, & Konté, 2020).

In recognition of the importance of diaspora diplomacy in Nigeria's public diplomacy, the Federal Government of Nigeria set up the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NiDCOM) in 2018. The main aim of this commission is to engage Nigerians in diaspora and encourage them to participate in Nigeria's development (Adebowale, & Ojo, 2025). This was a significant landmark in Nigeria's public diplomacy. It recognized diaspora diplomacy as a means to Nigeria's progress and positively affected its international image. Public diplomacy has become a strong engine for the attainment of Nigeria's economic objectives, combining the power of economic diplomacy and the country's brand. The core of this is the country's thriving entertainment industry, including Nollywood and Nigerian music, which have a global presence and therefore change the global narrative about the country. Nollywood is the world's biggest film industry, producing over 2,500 movies annually, which adds about \$7 billion to the country's economy (Endong, 2018). In addition to this, Nigeria continues to face a rough global image based on various issues such as corruption, insecurity, and governance challenges. Transparency International ranked Nigeria 149th out of 180 countries in the Corruption Perceptions Index in 2020, which negatively impacted Nigeria's global image (Transparency International, 2021). In addition to this, security concerns such as terrorism, banditry, and kidnapping have also negatively impacted Nigeria's global image and discouraged investors from investing in the country. From this, it is evident that a state's internal governance and global image have a direct correlation and impact on how successful public diplomacy is in promoting state interests. However, public diplomacy is essential in promoting Nigeria's interests in the modern world. Nigeria has progressively expanded its influence across the African continent and the world at large, from peacekeeping to diaspora engagement, as well as a combination of digital, cultural, and economic diplomacy.

Historical Evolution of Nigeria's Public Diplomacy in Promoting Nigeria's National Interests

Nigeria's public diplomacy has been growing hand-in-hand with its foreign policy interests since it gained independence in 1960. From the post-independence era to the present day, Nigeria has been relying on public diplomacy instruments such as peacekeeping, technical assistance, cultural exchanges, economic outreach, and diaspora engagement to advance its own interests. Nigeria's interests have been political independence and sovereignty, economic development, guiding African regional leadership, ensuring national security, and promoting Nigeria's socio-cultural values. All these interests have been guiding Nigeria's public diplomacy at both regional and global levels.

Nigeria's Foreign Policy Objectives

Nigeria's foreign policy, from the time of its independence, has largely focused on the African continent. The objectives of the policy have been clear from the beginning: to support the liberation movements across the continent, to advocate for peace, to encourage regional cooperation, and to enhance economic growth. In the 1960s and 1970s, the country's public diplomacy efforts were critical to its foreign policy objectives. For instance, Nigeria supported the anti-colonial movements in Angola, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, and South Africa by funding the movements, advocating for the movements at the diplomatic table, and participating in peacekeeping efforts (Ebegbulem, 2019). Nigeria's leadership roles in the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), which later became the African Union (AU), made the country a regional giant, a voice for the African continent, and a symbol of African leadership and cooperation. During the apartheid era, Nigeria donated more than \$60 million to the liberation movements in Southern Africa and provided scholarships to South African students. This, therefore, was a form of cultural and educational diplomacy (Ogunnubi, & Isike, 2018). All of the above activities, therefore, helped to enhance Nigeria's diplomatic power and to achieve its objectives of African solidarity and leadership.

Nigeria's Political Interests

Nigeria has used its public diplomacy to promote its sovereignty, protect its territorial integrity, and seek international recognition. A major way of attaining this has been through its peacekeeping activities, which are considered an expression of its political diplomacy. Nigeria has played a leading role in some of the most significant peacekeeping missions, such as the Congo in the early 1960s, Liberia between 1990 and 1997, Sierra Leone between 1999 and 2005, and Sudan in 2005. It has sent over 200,000 peacekeeping forces to West Africa between 1990 and 2005 (Ibrahim, & Babangida, 2025). Through its ECOMOG forces, Nigeria has helped bring peace and democracy to Liberia and Sierra Leone, thus increasing its power in the region. Nigeria's peacekeeping activities have increased its international recognition and reinforced its image as a powerful country, thus serving its political interests.

Nigeria's Economic Interests

Nigeria has used public diplomacy to further its economic interests, including economic diplomacy, trade relations, and diaspora diplomacy. In the 1980s, Nigeria adopted economic diplomacy as a foreign policy tool to attract foreign investment and boost trade. In recent times, in the 2000s and beyond, diaspora remittances have become one of the key drivers of Nigeria's economy and a key pillar of public diplomacy. According to the World Bank, Nigeria has been receiving about \$21 billion in diaspora remittances in 2018, which rose to about \$24 billion in 2020. By 2023, this figure has remained upwards of \$20 billion and is expected to continue growing, making Nigeria the leading recipient of diaspora remittances in Africa. This is a demonstration of how diaspora diplomacy is being used to further Nigeria's economic interests. Another example is how Nigeria is using its cultural influence through Nollywood and Nigerian music to promote economic and cultural diplomacy. Nollywood is the world's second-largest film industry in terms of the number of films it produces, churning out over 2,500 films annually, which adds about \$7 billion to the Nigerian economy (Igwe, 2017). Nigerian music has also gained international acclaim, increasing the country's cultural footprint and visibility across the globe. These sectors can be seen as instruments of public diplomacy, promoting the country's culture across the globe while at the same time increasing investment and tourism in the country.

Nigeria's Security Interests

Nigeria's security interests inform its public diplomacy. Nigeria engages in public diplomacy in the promotion of regional stability and national security through its involvement in peacekeeping operations, military diplomacy, and regional security cooperation. Nigeria has participated in more than 40 international peacekeeping operations across the globe since 1960. In addition, Nigeria has contributed more than 200,000 personnel to international peacekeeping operations (Ebegbulem, 2019). Nigeria's leadership in the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF), which was formed in 2015 to fight Boko Haram in the Lake Chad Basin region, is one example of military diplomacy that has advanced Nigeria's regional security interests and its national interests (Dauda, & Ukaeje, 2024). In essence, Nigeria has cemented its position as a regional security actor and has advanced its security interests and goals.

Nigeria's Socio-Cultural Interests

Nigeria has consistently utilized its culture as a bridge through diplomacy, student exchange programs, and technical assistance, sharing its culture with the world. One such initiative has been the Nigerian Technical Aid Corps (NTAC), established in 1987, where Nigerians have contributed to the development of African, Caribbean, and Pacific countries through the services of Nigerian professionals in the fields of education, health, engineering, and agriculture (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). Between 1987 and 2020, more than 10,000 Nigerian professionals were placed in over 40 countries through the NTAC program (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). The program has not only promoted the spread of Nigerian culture across the globe, but also strengthened its relations with other nations, thus increasing its soft power on the world stage. Along with the aforementioned, the cultural exports of Nigeria, such as Nollywood, Afrobeats, literary works, fashion, and sports, have further increased the reach and influence of Nigeria across the globe. Nigerian cultural diplomacy has enhanced Nigeria's image in the world. This is an example that cultural diplomacy is not limited to state actors; it also involves other non-state actors such as musicians, film makers, writers, and sportsmen who assist in projecting Nigeria's image in the world.

Nigeria's Regional and Global Interests

Nigeria has always maintained its focus on its own region and its position on the global stage by advocating for African unity and global recognition. Its foreign policy efforts have always pushed forward in this regard through its involvement with the United Nations, the African Union, and the Economic Community of West African States. Its peacekeeping efforts have helped stabilize the region, and this has increased its power and influence over its neighbors. Nigeria has provided peacekeeping forces to Liberia and Sierra Leone under the auspices of the Economic Community of West African States, which have helped these nations achieve democratic government. This, in turn, has increased Nigeria's power and influence over its neighbors (Ebegbulem, 2019). Nigeria has always provided leadership for the Economic Community of West African States and has acted as a mediator for several political crises, ranging from The Gambia in 2017 to Mali in 2013 and Guinea-Bissau in 2012. In the global sphere, Nigeria has relied on multilateral diplomacy to pursue its interests. Nigeria has served as a non-permanent member of the United Nations Security Council five times: (1966-1967), (1978-1979), (1994-1995), (2010-2011), and (2014-2015). This record has significantly increased Nigeria's power in global diplomacy, allowing it to have a voice in global peace and security deliberations (Osimen, Obiyan, Ayankoya, & Essien, 2024).

Nigeria's public diplomacy has undergone many changes in the course of decades. In the 1960s and 1970s, Nigeria's public diplomacy was based on its peace and liberation activities. In recent times, public diplomacy has included economic diplomacy, diaspora engagement, digital diplomacy, and cultural exchange.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the study, Ogunnubi and Isike (2018) examine Nigeria's soft power using a qualitative method and Joseph Nye's framework to analyze Nigeria's soft power resources. According to this study, Nigeria's influence in Africa is not based on military and economic

might, but on soft power resources such as Nollywood, music, peacekeeping, Technical Aid Corps, and proactive diplomacy across Africa. From this study, it is evident that Nigeria possesses immense soft power resources that could help entrench its leadership position in Africa, but these resources are being undermined by ills such as corruption, insecurity, poor governance, and lack of coordination within institutions. The authors opined that Nigeria's soft power is not being maximized and is not well coordinated. However, this study differs from this idea in that it focuses more on soft power as a tool for influence in Africa, while this study takes a broader view of public diplomacy as a strategic tool for promoting Nigeria's interests in the 21st century, including political, economic, security, socio-cultural, and global dimensions.

In the article "Attractions and Limitations of Nigeria's Soft Power" written by Tella (2017), the author employed qualitative methods with the guidance of the constructivist theory. In the article, the author posited that Nigeria's soft power comes from its democracy, peacekeeping role, Nollywood, music, and the Technical Aid Corps, which all enhance Nigeria's image and power in Africa. However, the study also reveals the contradictory situation that despite the huge reservoir of Nigeria's soft power, the country's foreign image is marred by internal challenges like the Boko Haram insurgency, corruption, human rights violations, and bad governance. The study asserts that Nigeria's capacity to exert soft power and practice successful public diplomacy is largely dependent on political stability and governance reform at the domestic level. The study differs from existing literature in that it focuses on soft power and Nigeria's image in Africa, while this study examines public diplomacy in a more general sense and how it can be used to advance Nigeria's interests in the 21st century.

Anaele (2014), in his article titled "Nigeria's Foreign Policy and Citizen Diplomacy: Under President Goodluck Jonathan," uses historical research methods; his study is based on secondary sources such as textbooks, articles in journals, and official documents. The study is important because it shows that citizen diplomacy is significant in Nigeria's foreign policy because of how Nigerians are treated and cared for in other countries. The findings of the study indicate that citizen diplomacy can improve Nigeria's image in other countries by protecting Nigerians in other countries and by encouraging Nigerians in other countries to help improve Nigeria's image. The study concludes that citizen diplomacy is an important strategy in advancing Nigeria's foreign policy. However, there is a major difference between this study and the study by Anaele: while his study focuses on citizen diplomacy in particular years of governance in Nigeria, this study focuses on public diplomacy as a whole and how it is used to advance Nigeria's national interests in general in the 21st century.

A perusal of literature reveals that scholars have analyzed Nigeria public diplomacy from different perspectives. These perspectives include soft power public diplomacy, citizen public diplomacy, diaspora public diplomacy, and technical aid public diplomacy. However, most scholars have focused more on the micro aspects of public diplomacy rather than its macro approach as a cohesive and strategic instrument for advancing Nigeria's national interests. In addition, most scholars have focused more on Nigeria's power in Africa without delving into the ways in which public diplomacy can be used to advance Nigeria's political interests, economic interests, security interests, socio-cultural interests, regional interests, and global interests in the 21st century. This is a gap that has not been filled in the literature. This study will fill this gap by using public diplomacy as a multidimensional instrument of national power to examine its role in advancing Nigeria's interests in the modern global system.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Soft Power Theory

The paper employed the theory of soft power as its theoretical framework. The theory was first proposed by Joseph Nye in 1990. This theory helps understand how nations achieve their objectives by attracting others rather than forcing them. According to Nye (2004), soft power can be defined as "the ability of a country to shape the preferences of others through appeal, to get others to want what you want." This contrasts with hard power, which is based on military power and sanctions. On the other hand, soft power is based on less tangible assets like diplomacy, culture, international reputation, student and academic exchanges, media, and aid. One area that stands out is public diplomacy, which is a tool for soft power. Public diplomacy is about engaging with people in other nations, influencing how they see a particular nation, and promoting one's interests without using force or aggression. In the modern world, soft power is a dominant aspect in global relations, driven by globalization and technological advances that enable nations to influence global publics through culture and information.

However, despite its importance, the Soft Power Theory has received criticism from various researchers. According to some researchers, for instance, it is tricky to measure the effect of soft power, as attraction and perception are not tangible or objective, making it difficult to measure the effect on foreign policies (Ji, 2023).

Soft Power Theory is relevant to this study because it demonstrates how public diplomacy can be employed to achieve Nigeria's national interests. Here, public diplomacy is considered an independent variable, and Nigeria's national interest covering all aspects of its interests in politics, economics, security, socio-cultural issues, regions, and global issues is considered the dependent variable. According to this theory, public diplomacy can be employed to enhance a nation's appeal and legitimacy. This appeal and legitimacy can be used to advance its national interests. For instance, this theory suggests that public diplomacy can be employed to enhance Nigeria's global appeal and legitimacy. This appeal and legitimacy can be used to advance Nigeria's national interests in the 21st century. On one side, public diplomacy and poor national image can be used to limit Nigeria's ability to achieve its national interests.

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From this analysis, it is clear that Soft Power Theory is relevant to this study because it provides the theoretical framework for understanding public diplomacy's role in shaping Nigeria's national interest in the 21st century.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative research methodology and relies on secondary sources of data collection to examine the role of public diplomacy in promoting Nigeria's national interest in the 21st century. Data were sourced from academic journals, textbooks, official government publications, policy documents, reports from international organisations such as the World Bank and United Nations, and publications from the Nigerian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Nigerians in Diaspora Commission. The study adopted a descriptive and analytical research design, which enabled the researcher to examine Nigeria's public diplomacy strategies such as cultural diplomacy, diaspora diplomacy, economic diplomacy, digital diplomacy, and peacekeeping diplomacy, and analyse how these instruments contribute to the promotion of Nigeria's political, economic, security, socio-cultural, regional, and global interests. Data collected were analysed using content analysis, where relevant information from documents and reports were systematically reviewed and interpreted to establish the relationship between public diplomacy and Nigeria's national interest.

Public Diplomacy Instruments Used by Nigeria

Public diplomacy has thus become an important instrument for the achievement of Nigeria's interests in the contemporary world. The country has used various forms of public diplomacy, such as cultural and media diplomacy, information through technology, diaspora diplomacy, economic and military diplomacy, peacekeeping, and educational and exchange programs, to shape its image, promote its economic growth, enhance its diplomatic relations, and strengthen its security. These forms of public diplomacy have enabled the country to influence the opinions of international publics, promote its culture, attract investments, and increase its power in the world (Nye, 2004; Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018).

Cultural Diplomacy

Cultural diplomacy is one area that has proven to be very effective in Nigeria's public diplomacy through Nollywood, music, literature, fashion, and sports. Nollywood is known globally as the second largest film industry in the world and is considered one of Nigeria's major cultural exports and soft power assets (Afolabi, Onikoyi, & Okpadah, 2022). Nollywood contributed about 2.3% to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product in 2016, which is equivalent to ₦239 billion. This demonstrates its economic and diplomatic potential ((Afolabi, Onikoyi, & Okpadah, 2022). Music, especially Afrobeat music, has gained momentum globally and has seen Nigerian artistes performing on global platforms and receiving global awards. This has contributed to Nigeria's cultural diplomacy.

Media Diplomacy

It is about using media and communication channels to promote Nigeria's foreign policy interests and enhance its international image. Nigeria has always relied on international broadcasting to articulate its foreign policy position and promote a positive national image abroad since 1961. This has been done primarily through the Voice of Nigeria (VON), which has been instrumental in broadcasting Nigeria's foreign policy position to the entire world and projecting a positive national image abroad since 1961 (Saka, Ayaka, & Alkali, 2025). In addition to this, other media stations in Nigeria, including the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), and international media collaborations have also played a significant role in projecting Nigeria to the international community. In essence, media diplomacy in Nigeria is aimed at influencing the international perception of Nigeria, promoting its foreign policies, and countering negative perceptions in the international arena (Manor, 2019).

Digital Diplomacy (Social Media and International Broadcasting)

Nigeria is embracing digital diplomacy by using various social media platforms such as X (Twitter), Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube to connect with global audiences and craft Nigeria's image in foreign policy. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Nigeria is using these platforms to engage in digital diplomacy by sharing information regarding Nigeria's foreign policy decisions, investment opportunities in Nigeria, as well as connecting with Nigerians in the diaspora. Digital diplomacy in Nigeria is becoming even more important since 2010 as these platforms were gaining popularity in international communication/public diplomacy. Digital diplomacy is important in that it enables Nigeria to directly engage global audiences in international affairs, respond quickly to global events, and broadcast its foreign policy ambitions in real-time. Digital diplomacy is considered an important component of national image in the 21st century by various scholars.

Diaspora Diplomacy

Diaspora diplomacy emerges as one of the key public diplomacy instruments in Nigeria in the 21st century due to the presence of a significant population in diaspora and their economic contributions to Nigeria in terms of remittances and investments. According to the World Bank, Nigeria received diaspora remittances of about \$21 billion in 2018. This figure has been rising to about \$24 billion in 2020. This has positioned Nigeria as the highest remittance-receiving country in Africa (World Bank, 2019; World Bank, 2021). In 2023, diaspora remittances have been rising to more than \$20 billion annually. This has greatly contributed to Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings and its economic development. The establishment of the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission (NiDCOM)

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in 2018 has recognised diaspora diplomacy as one of the key public diplomacy instruments in Nigeria (Adepoju, 2019). This has helped Nigeria in advancing its economic development and its international image. Both are in line with Nigeria's economic and political interests.

Economic Diplomacy

Economic diplomacy can be cited as one of the important public diplomacy strategies used by Nigeria. This is done with the objective of increasing trade, attracting investments, and advancing economic cooperation. This is done through various institutions like the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC), the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC), and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Nigeria also works with international economic groups like ECOWAS, the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), the World Trade Organization (WTO), and others. This helps Nigeria to increase its trade and investment opportunities (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018).

Military Diplomacy and Peacekeeping Diplomacy

The military diplomacy and peacekeeping activities can be viewed as important instruments in Nigeria's public diplomacy and foreign policy. Nigeria has been involved in United Nations peace support operations since 1960. It has deployed its soldiers to Congo, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Mali, and The Gambia (Ebegbulem, 2019). Nigeria has also played a central role in ECOMOG interventions in Liberia and Sierra Leone from 1990 to 2005. It has deployed thousands of soldiers and significant resources to establish and maintain peace and democracy in those countries (Ebegbulem, 2019).

Educational and Exchange Diplomacy

Educational and exchange diplomacy is a major tool of Nigerian public diplomacy. The Nigerian Technical Aid Corps (NTAC), which was established in 1987, has, over the years, sent Nigerian professionals, including teachers, doctors, engineers, and other technical experts, to developing nations across Africa, the Caribbean, and the Pacific, as part of the country's foreign policy (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). So far, the Nigerian Technical Aid Corps has sent Nigerian professionals to more than 40 nations across the world, thereby enhancing cultural exchange and strengthening diplomatic ties with the beneficiary nations (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). Through educational diplomacy, Nigeria seeks to consolidate its image as a country committed to development cooperation, human capacity building, and regional integration.

ROLE OF PUBLIC DIPLOMACY IN PROMOTING NIGERIA'S NATIONAL INTEREST

Public Diplomacy and Nigeria's International Image

Public diplomacy has played an instrumental role in the development and enhancement of Nigeria's image on the global scene, particularly through its peacekeeping activities. Since attaining its independence in 1960, Nigeria has relied on peacekeeping as an integral part of its public diplomacy, with the aim of enhancing its image on the global scene. Nigeria has contributed to the United Nations peacekeeping efforts in the Congo (1960), Lebanon (1978), Liberia (1990), Sierra Leone (1999), Sudan (2005), and Mali (2013), thus enhancing its image as a peacekeeping and stability-providing country on the African continent (Ebegbulem, 2019). Of particular interest is the fact that, between 1990 and 2005, Nigeria contributed more than 200,000 troops to Liberia and Sierra Leone through the ECOMOG force, thus becoming the largest West African troop-contributing country (Ebegbulem, 2019).

Public Diplomacy and Foreign Policy Objectives

Public diplomacy has traditionally been one of the tools Nigeria has relied on in advancing its foreign policy agenda, especially in the development of regional peace, advancing economic diplomacy, and advancing foreign policy on the international stage. Nigeria's foreign policy has traditionally focused on the African continent first, with the primary focus on maintaining peace in the region, addressing conflicts in the region, and the need for African unity (Ojo, 2016). Nigeria has relied on public diplomacy in mediating conflicts in Liberia, Sierra Leone, and The Gambia in advancing regional peace and democracy (Ebegbulem, 2019). Nigeria has also relied on public diplomacy in advancing multilateral diplomacy through the Economic Community of West African States, the African Union, and the United Nations in advancing foreign policy and national interests (Akinterinwa, 2014). This demonstrates the role public diplomacy has played in advancing Nigeria's foreign policy and diplomatic interests on the international stage.

Public Diplomacy and Economic Development/FDI

Public diplomacy has also played a pivotal role in Nigeria's economic development, especially in the area of diaspora remittances, economic diplomacy, and the encouragement of foreign direct investments. According to the World Bank, Nigeria has continued to receive diaspora remittances of about \$21 billion in 2018 and \$24 billion in 2020, thus becoming the leading recipient of diaspora remittances in Africa (World Bank, 2021). In 2023, the diaspora remittances have continued to remain above \$20 billion annually, thus becoming instrumental in Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings and growth. In 2021, the Central Bank of Nigeria launched the 'Naira 4 Dollar Scheme,' which has seen the country receive over \$2.4 billion in diaspora remittances (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021). This has had the effect of encouraging the development of houses and the creation of employment opportunities, thus

contributing to Nigeria's growth and foreign policy interests (Chukwueme, 2026). Therefore, public diplomacy has continued to play a pivotal role in Nigeria's growth and foreign exchange earnings.

Public Diplomacy and National Security

Public diplomacy has a significant role to play in Nigeria's national security by integrating regional security alliances, peacekeeping diplomacy, and counterterrorism cooperation into the fabric of the nation. For instance, the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF), formed in 2015 to fight Boko Haram in the Lake Chad region, demonstrates the role public diplomacy can play in strengthening national security by bringing nations together to fight common regional and international security challenges (Albert, 2017). Nigeria's public diplomacy has helped to heighten cooperation and coordination between Nigeria and its neighboring countries, Chad, Niger, and Cameroon, in sharing intelligence and coordinating military operations to fight terrorism in the region (Albert, 2017). Nigeria's involvement in international peacekeeping operations has also helped to heighten military cooperation and intelligence sharing between Nigeria and other countries in the region, thereby strengthening Nigeria's national security (Adebajo, 2019). In conclusion, public diplomacy has a significant role to play in strengthening Nigeria's national security by heightening military cooperation and intelligence sharing and strengthening regional security alliances.

Public Diplomacy and Regional Leadership in Africa

Nigeria has continued to build itself into a regional role model in Africa through its public diplomacy. By engaging in diplomatic mediation, peacekeeping, and technical assistance, Nigeria has continued to foster peace and cooperation in West Africa. Its peacekeeping roles in Liberia and Sierra Leone under the auspices of the Economic Community of West African States have continued to play a crucial role in restoring democracy and peace, thereby giving Nigeria more influence in the region (Adepoju, 2019). In addition, Nigeria intervened as a mediator during the political crisis that struck The Gambia in 2017. This ensured a peaceful transition of power, thereby giving Nigeria more influence in the region (Albert, 2017). Since 1987, Nigeria has continued to establish its influence in Africa by sending its professionals to other African, Caribbean, and Pacific nations under the auspices of its Technical Aid Corps. This has continued to reinforce its diplomatic ties and give Nigeria more influence in these regions (Ogunnubi & Isike, 2018). All these public diplomacy roles have continued to give Nigeria more influence on the continent.

Poor International Image and Reputation Issues

Nigeria's public diplomacy efforts are also affected by the country's bad international image, which has resulted from the challenges of corruption and insecurity in the country. Nigeria has continuously ranked low in the global ranking of good governance and the fight against corruption. This has further undermined Nigeria's international credibility. For example, using the Corrupt Perception Index, Nigeria ranked 154th out of 180 in the year 2021, improved slightly in 2023 to 145th, and in 2024 ranked 140th on the index, indicating the challenges of corruption in the country (Transparency International, 2024). In addition, the economic implications of corruption in Nigeria are also huge. Estimates indicate that Nigeria has lost over 400 billion dollars between 1960 and 2015 due to corruption in the country, which has undermined the country's public diplomacy efforts (Arowolo, 2022).

Strengthening Cultural Diplomacy

Nigeria's cultural diplomacy is an area where the country has excelled in engaging the public, given its rich cultural fabric, the popularity of its films across the globe, the dynamism of its music, and its rich cultural heritage. The country, therefore, needs to promote its films, songs, arts, and festivals across the globe through its missions and cultural centers. Cultural exchanges, international festivals, and exchange programs will also help spread Nigeria's culture and values far and wide. Nollywood and Afrobeats have already made Nigeria the cultural capital of the world, and the government needs to collaborate with these sectors to create an image for the world. Cultural diplomacy will, in the long run, help the country rise to higher heights, attract more tourists, and strengthen its relations with other countries.

Engagement with Nigerian Diaspora

Nigeria's diaspora is also notable as an important resource for the country's public diplomacy. The diaspora has a significant effect on the country's economy. For instance, the diaspora remits, invests, transfers technology, and develops skills. However, for the diaspora to contribute maximally to the country's development, the government needs to enhance diaspora diplomacy. The government should develop policies that will encourage diaspora investment, diaspora bonds, knowledge transfer, and the inclusion of diaspora voices in the development agenda. The Nigerian missions should have constant interactions with the diaspora and incorporate them into the country's public diplomacy. The Nigerians in the Diaspora Commission should also be strengthened to ensure the success of the diaspora engagement programs. The success of the diaspora diplomacy will ensure the country attracts investment, boosts its image, and promotes its interests on the global stage.

Inter-Agency Coordination

Effective public diplomacy requires close collaboration between the government institutions that make up the foreign policy. It also requires collaboration in the flow of information, culture, tourism, trade, and investment promotion. In Nigeria, public diplomacy activities are carried out by different institutions without a general plan. This has resulted in duplication of work and inconsistency

in messages. The solution to this problem is obvious. It requires collaboration between the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Information and Culture, the Nigerians in the Diaspora Commission, the Ministry of Trade and Investment, the Nigerian Tourism Development Authority, and the security agencies. Forming an inter-agency public diplomacy committee will ensure that all institutions in Nigeria are working together to promote a common narrative regarding Nigeria's foreign policy and interests.

Public-Private Partnership in Diplomacy

Public diplomacy is no longer solely the government's responsibility. Other players like private businesses, media houses, and civil society organizations have become integral parts. Nigeria should adopt public-private partnerships in public diplomacy by engaging Nollywood, the Nigerian music industry, sports organizations, universities, and private businesses. For example, imagine multinationals like Globacom, First Bank, MTN, and Arik Airlines operating abroad and acting as ambassadors for Nigeria's economic diplomacy. Universities can be used to advance educational diplomacy by organizing student exchange programs. This will help increase Nigeria's diplomatic scope and enhance its international image.

CONCLUSION

This research examines the role of public diplomacy in the development of Nigeria's national interests in the modern world. The research reveals how public diplomacy has emerged as an important instrument in Nigeria's foreign policy, which is used to achieve the country's political, economic, security, socio-cultural, regional, and global interests. The research also reveals the history of public diplomacy in Nigeria, which has evolved from liberation and peacekeeping activities in the 1960s and 1970s, to economic diplomacy in the 1980s, citizen diplomacy in the 2000s, and finally to diaspora and digital diplomacy in the 21st century. The research also reveals some of the instruments used by Nigeria in its public diplomacy, such as peacekeeping, the Technical Aid Corps, Nollywood, remittance, cultural exchange, regional mediation, and digital communication. These tools have allowed Nigeria to enhance its position of leadership on the African continent, attract foreign capital, strengthen its diplomatic relations, spread its culture across the globe, and raise its international image. The research also points out that diaspora remittance, cultural export, and peacekeeping activities remain some of the most powerful tools of public diplomacy for Nigeria in the 21st century.

Based on these findings, it is possible to develop some policy recommendations. These include: Nigeria needs to develop an overall national public diplomacy strategy that articulates national interests, national public diplomacy goals, target audiences, as well as methods of communication. Digital diplomacy is an area that needs improvement. The online presence of Nigerian embassies needs to be enhanced. Additionally, there is a need to utilize strategic communication to project Nigeria's image abroad. The cultural diplomacy of Nigeria needs improvement by focusing on Nollywood productions, Nigerian music, fashion, sports, as well as cultural festivals as tools of soft power in image projection. Diaspora diplomacy is an area that needs to be supported by stronger policy instruments to encourage diaspora investment in Nigeria, as well as to develop diaspora bonds and knowledge transfer programs. Coordination among various government agencies dealing in foreign policy, trade, tourism, culture, as well as information management needs to be enhanced to improve public diplomacy in Nigeria. Nigeria needs to develop an image of itself to the world by developing a nation branding strategy.

Public diplomacy remains an important element in the promotion of Nigeria's interests in the contemporary world. If well-coordinated and executed, public diplomacy has the capacity to elevate Nigeria's image globally, enhance diplomatic relations, attract foreign investments, promote Nigerian culture, enhance security cooperation, and sustain Nigeria's leading role in Africa and the world at large. Therefore, Nigeria should make public diplomacy the core of her foreign policy if she is to effectively protect and promote her interests in the contemporary world.

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